

Activating Higher Order Thinking Skills in the EFL Classroom: A Four Cs Approach to Soft-CLIL

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Abstract: *This paper outlines a classroom project designed to activate students' higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) through developing, delivering, and responding to informed opinions. Participants were required to develop, deliver, and respond to informed opinions within a university English program to help prepare them to enrol in undergraduate courses at English-medium universities abroad. The project incorporated a peer learning element in each activity where participants shared their opinions to peers via speech, recordings, and group discussion. Peer and instructor feedback was provided throughout the process. Results from one-to-one interviews and observations from the facilitator indicated that Coyle's (1999) Four Cs approach to CLIL was an effective framework to plan the project and achieve improvements in meaningful L2 use and exchange. This led to increased awareness of the importance of HOTS and improvement in the participant's ability to apply, analyze, evaluate, and create their positions on various aspects related to international issues.*

Keywords: CLIL, critical thinking, peer learning, study abroad.

Introduction

Few would disagree that critical thinking skills are vital to student academic success. Many western universities publish information on their websites citing the relationship between academic achievement and a student's ability to assess and analyze evidence to make reasoned judgements. For EFL students preparing to study academic subjects at universities abroad, developing critical thinking skills, concurrently with improving their L2 competence, is essential for increasing their chances of success.

At the core of the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach to language learning is achieving an "equitable balance" between learning content together with specific language learning goals and focuses on increasing critical thinking abilities (Coyle, 2007). In the case of the study reported here, the participants were English majors with varying degrees of knowledge about international issues. As a result, a soft-CLIL approach was used with more emphasis on language learning tasks (specifically developing, delivering, and responding to an informed opinion), and the

project was undertaken with the Four Cs approach to CLIL (content, cognition, communication, and culture) used as a framework in the planning stage.

The project aimed to provide students with more opportunities to activate HOTS through developing and delivering informed opinions while increasing knowledge about international issues. Previous interviews with students who had returned from studying abroad revealed that the inability to convey their opinions on class material in academic settings was an obstacle to participating in their classes. The belief underpinning the project was that students needed specific instruction on how to develop an informed opinion. They also needed to practice their delivery, and learn how to respond to opposing opinions from their peers.

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) and the 4 Cs Framework

The CLIL approach to language education is rooted in European bilingual education pedagogy. The most relevant description of CLIL for the project outlined in this paper comes from Marsh (2002), who defines it as a setting where class subjects are taught through a foreign language with “dual-focused aims”, specifically, learning content while simultaneously learning foreign language skills (p. 2). This definition highlights the importance of foreign language learning in CLIL classrooms and why it can be a viable approach in EFL classrooms. The use of CLIL in EFL settings requires careful consideration of how to meet language-learning goals. While lessons focus on the content, specific language learning objectives stem from content learning, and the degree to which one is prioritized over the other depends on the learners. For students with higher L2 proficiency and specific knowledge of the target content, a “hard-CLIL” approach in which the focus on the content is more heavily weighted is required. Conversely, for students with less L2 proficiency, a “soft-CLIL” approach in which the balance tilts towards the target language skills would be better suited. Ikeda (2013) adds that the version of CLIL employed in the foreign language classroom also depends on the instructor’s “training of CLIL principles and skills” (p. 32).

Coyle (2007) and Coyle, Hood, and Marsh (2010) agree that the CLIL approach is ideal when there is an equal balance of the content and language learning goals, but the emphasis can shift to either depending on the learning objective. Syllabus planning from a CLIL approach is often based on Coyle’s (1999) Four Cs Framework: content, cognition, communication, and culture. Educators must ensure lessons follow Coyle’s (1999) mantra of “learn to use language and use language to learn” to integrate content with language learning objectives effectively. The content in the Four Cs is crucial to creating a pedagogically sound teaching activity. As Llinares, Morton, and Whittaker (2012) contend, “students need to learn content through language, and language through content” (p. 189). EFL practitioners must choose appropriate content and associated activities that encourage learning, promote interest in the subject and are comprehensible to the students to ensure this reciprocal learning occurs. The cognition element of the framework relies heavily on student-centered learning and requires learners to develop cognitive skills and interpret complex authentic (or scaffolded) content as they advance toward higher levels of critical thinking. These skills do not develop independently; they must be cultivated through instruction, practice, and peer learning activities. Students develop critical thinking skills through tasks that promote peer learning (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Cognition and culture surpass the dual focus of language and content to include higher level thinking skills and cultural awareness. Cognition is connected to

communication as students work together with support from the instructor to acquire the content. They reach the stage of using meaningful communication to discuss, evaluate, and reproduce the content. Finally, the culture element refers to students gaining more international understanding and awareness. Pham and Koseki (2016) point out that “fostering globally-minded” people is a significant tenet of CLIL. For EFL students preparing to study abroad, the necessity to increase HOTS and understand world issues are valuable skills.

Informed opinions and international issues

Intermediate and advanced EFL students do not typically have difficulties voicing their opinions. However, when asked to provide reasons or support for their opinions, the same students often need help to meet this request and tend to rely on their personal experiences or beliefs to reason their position. This deficiency becomes particularly problematic in academic settings when discussing class content.

Building on the definition of informed opinion as beliefs, judgments or ways of thinking based on information, the project pushed students to think of informed opinions as based on a deep understanding of facts and results after carefully considering varying viewpoints. An opinion typically starts with a question followed by gathering information before deciding one’s opinion, but an informed opinion includes a critical thinking element after the gathering information stage. Informed opinions can only come to fruition after considering other points of view, including those that differ from one’s stance. Within Bloom’s taxonomy, lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) includes recognising and recalling facts. In contrast, HOTS includes more advanced cognitive skills such as applying, analysing, evaluating and synthesising information (Bloom, Engelhart, Furst, Hill, & Krathwohl, 1956).

Most participants had little difficulty remembering key facts from the unit content materials. However, it required explicit instruction and practice to analyse and evaluate those facts to form their opinions. Critical thinking is a central component when creating an informed opinion and a skill that EFL students need support to develop.

Some view EFL classrooms as having the potential to implement curriculums that focus on teaching international issues. (Cates, 1990; 2002, Osler & Starkey, 2005) Specifically, in Japanese universities, Cates (2002) and Peaty (2004) point out that increasing critical thinking skills, promoting global citizenship, and stimulating student interaction are benefits of such an approach. These potential outcomes mirror MEXT’s (2014) initiative to produce more globally-minded students who can reason and communicate actively. While this project focused on international issues as the content element, other fields of study would be suitable if consideration was given to the students’ levels, interests, and academic majors or backgrounds.

Context

At the time of writing, 33 (23 female and ten male) 1st-year university students participated in the course unit on developing informed opinions. The participants in the study were from the English course in three intact classes at a private university in western Japan. The test score range for students in this study was from 480–610 on the TOEFL IBT proficiency test. All participants were in the preparation stage before a one-year study abroad program.

Based on past interviews conducted with students who had returned from study abroad programs, difficulty in fully participating in discussions with their peers both inside and outside the classroom involving academic topics was found. This difficulty mainly resulted from students needing to be made aware that it is common for interlocutors to reference facts from course resources to support their thoughts and opinions. While about half of those interviewed believed their ability to convey an informed opinion improved while studying abroad, the other half reported that they often remained silent during such exchanges. Most interviewees agreed that more practice and awareness are necessary before departing for study abroad programs. Based on this information, a project was planned to give students more opportunities to form and deliver informed opinions.

Rationale

All the students in this study planned to embark on one-year study abroad programs in English-medium universities. The project was designed to help students make the leap from passive class participants to active contributors. However, actively participating in class discussions was one of the main hurdles during their time abroad. Many reported feeling intimidated and unaware that academic sources were often referenced in class and group discussions. As a result, many students chose to remain silent in such situations. It was decided to give students more opportunities to prepare and deliver their opinions based on the class content (readings, lectures, and video sources on international issues).

This approach aimed to increase students' ability to develop an informed opinion, stress the necessity for such a skill, and increase confidence levels by improving fluency and accuracy through peer and instructor feedback. It was decided that if students were more knowledgeable about the importance of improving critical thinking skills by creating an informed opinion and had more opportunities through tasks, it could lead to a more successful study abroad experience. A further goal was to increase awareness of international issues and promote global citizenship by developing their opinions and through reflection.

The Project

Within a semester-long course, participants completed a unit of work covering six class periods. The subject of the unit was international issues and students had to complete the task of developing opinions based on class materials covering issues such as child labour, child soldiers, and landmines. The project consisted of three distinct activities; developing an informed opinion, creating an audio or video recording, and finally participating in a tutorial-style setting in which they can voice their opinions and oppose others. Students worked together to develop their opinions using peer and instructor feedback for reflection and revision. All participants followed the same five-step pattern for creating an informed opinion with limitations imposed to ensure succinctness.

The first step was briefly introducing the issue in one or two sentences. The second phase also has a two-sentence limit in which students must explain causes of the problem. The causes of the issue must be directly paraphrased or summarized from a class reading or another credible source. In step three, the students must openly and directly state their opinion in one sentence. To complete the fourth step, students had to locate and paraphrase information that supports their viewpoint. This information typically came from class materials or other credible sources. This

step also had a limitation of two sentences. The informed opinion should finish with a concluding thought or summary. Students are given the choice of delivering steps two through four in any order they see fit. The five steps were chosen to provide students with the awareness of what a complete opinion includes, but additional instruction was provided explaining that some of the steps might not be necessary depending on the circumstances. For example, in instances where a previous interlocutor has already introduced the issue of discussion, then step one would become redundant. For samples that include each of the steps, see student examples 1 and 2 below.

For the second phase of the project, students created short video or audio recordings of themselves voicing their opinions to share with classmates. The peer viewers were then required to provide feedback designed to improve their opinions. The peer feedback covered language competence (word choice and grammar), paralanguage (tone, loudness, speed, and inflexion), and most importantly a critical thinking check. For the final portion of feedback, peer-reviewers checked if the support for the opinion was reasonable by checking the sources used.

The international issues unit concluded with a tutorial-style activity where the class was divided into two groups. Students practiced voicing their opinions based on prompts provided by the instructor. Then within each group participants take stands to support or oppose their classmates' opinions. For this part of the project, students pre-prepared supporting or opposing views on the international issues covered in the unit.

Student Example 1

Landmines – Opinion

Landmines are a controversial problem in the world because they kill or injure civilians and make land unusable for decades. One of the main reasons why armies still use landmines is their price. Landmines are cheap so that they can be used in large numbers to empty territory, destroy food sources, or terror. In my opinion, landmines must not be manufactured and used as soon as possible. Therefore, as the reading states, 40 countries which have yet to sign the Mine Ban Treaty, especially the US, China and Russia should sign the treaty and destroy their stockpile of mines. In addition, celebrities can help to raise international awareness of the landmine problems. As celebrities get involved the problems, the world will know more about people who are damaged by landmines. To sum up, countries, which have yet to sign the treaty, should be pressured to stop landmines, and individual effort are necessary to solve the problem.

Student Example 2

Child soldiers – Opinion

The use of children as soldiers in armed conflicts is a serious global issue. Child soldiers are any children under 18 who are recruited by both country and private armed groups and used as fighters, spies, suicide bombers, or sexual purpose. There are various reasons why recruiters target children. For example, children are more obedient and more easily manipulated than adults, and also children who are poor, or separated from their families or communities join the military to seek safety and the sense of belonging. In my opinion,

international community must prohibit both national and private armed groups from using child soldiers. In order to solve the issue, international community should make an international law with which have legitimacy for getting both national and private armed groups to comply, and keep up the pressure to countries to sign it. Also, according to the article, governments must support non-governmental organizations working to end child soldiers. To sum up, governments and NGOs should work together in order to stop child soldiers soon.

As stated earlier, the students participating in this project were English language majors; therefore, a soft-CLIL approach was adopted using scaffolding methods. Specifically, peer learning was used in the form of group work, where students had specific tasks related to the class materials and then shared their work. As a facilitator, I also provided extra instruction through supplementary readings, short lectures, videos, and explanations related to the issues. Once the students established a sound understanding of the class materials and the issue, they set about forming their opinions.

Assessment of the project took place through one-to-one interviews and observations from the instructor. Coyle's (1999) Four Cs Framework was referred to in the project's planning regarding the informed opinion task and facilitator observations. Results from interviews indicate that students placed a high value on the peer interaction aspect of the project and believed their ability to develop and deliver opinions improved. Students also reported gaining a deeper understanding of world problems and recognition of the impact of their actions. This type of awareness and global understanding closely follows the cultural aspect of the Four Cs Framework. From a facilitator standpoint, using the Four Cs Framework was, as Coyle (2007) points out, fundamental in the planning stage as the outcomes mirrored the theory. For instance, one of the communication goals is to have students produce authentic language, which was displayed through the creation of informed opinions (See examples 1 and 2 above) and during the larger group discussions.

Furthermore, within cognition or learning, through peer interactions and understanding of the content presented in the unit of work, the participants reproduced (steps 2 and 4 of the informed opinion) core sections of the text in their own words by paraphrasing and summarizing. The goal of students using HOTS to assess, evaluate, and synthesize the content improved slightly. However, as the two student examples show, the reasons supporting their opinions did not display evidence of synthesizing different sources.

Results

The results of the interviews seem to indicate that the project outcomes correspond with the Four Cs Framework used in the planning stage. Regarding the content, about 60% of the participants mentioned the content appealing to their interests. For example, one student stated, "After completing all the class readings, I want to study these problems more." As stated earlier, the choice of content is vital when planning from a CLIL approach. The second "C", cognition (or learning), was also heavily referenced in the results, with more than half of respondents mentioning their ability to understand the international issues covered in the class readings. One participant stated: "As for the opinions, I could gradually come to understand how to do them better." This comment indicates that some of the participant's ability to understand the content improved over the course of the project. The communication element of the framework was also often mentioned during interviews. Comments such as, "Working with classmates was really useful to improve my opinion."

and “The readings were difficult for me, but I could understand them with help from my partner.” appear to illustrate that participants placed a high value on peer interactions. Finally, 60% of the interviewees mentioned becoming more aware of the importance of knowing about international issues or recognizing their impact or place in connection with these issues. For example, one student stated, “Before this class, I didn’t know well about these problems.” Another stated, “I realized how lucky it is to be from Japan, compared with some developing countries.” These comments suggest that the fourth tenet of the Four Cs methodology, culture or, more specifically, cultural awareness or understanding, was partially achieved through this project.

Through observation and assessment, the facilitator noted a marked improvement in the quality of the informed opinions and that the participants appeared to appreciate the peer learning aspect of the project. This outcome parallels Boud’s (2001) findings that peer learning leads to students feeling more connected to the learning process. Concerning cognitive improvement, while HOTS, such as assessing, evaluating, and synthesizing information, did not improve dramatically, the ability to reproduce core text elements through summary and paraphrasing and then use that information to establish opinions significantly improved from the initial opinions to the final versions. This indicates that the cognition element of the Four Cs Framework was represented in the results.

Approximately 15% of the participants reported opposing viewpoints about the project. Most of these comments were connected to the difficulty of the readings. For example, one participant said, “For me, the readings were too difficult and not interesting.” Another negative comment was, “It was troublesome to make video and my opinions with the readings and say to friends.” These comments show that, for some of the participants, the content (international issues) did not match their expectations for the class, or they might not have identified improvements in their abilities through the peer learning and scaffolding activities associated with the project.

Limitations

This action research project lacked detailed quantitative analysis related to testing the effectiveness of using the Four Cs Framework approach to teach specific language-learning tasks. A more data-driven study could be used to generalize the results to the broader university EFL setting. Although the results of this project point toward the participants improving their ability to deliver an informed opinion and gaining an understanding of critical thinking skills, further investigations of how this approach affected the participants while studying abroad is necessary to determine the true success of the project. Potentially, this could be achieved by interviewing students after participating in study abroad programs.

Conclusions

This paper has highlighted a classroom project designed to increase students’ abilities to tackle content and produce authentic output in the form of informed opinions on international issues through a Four Cs approach to CLIL. Previous interviews with study abroad returnees found that fully participating by giving an informed opinion in academic settings was a high hurdle. It was decided to plan a project that would allow participants to craft and deliver their informed opinions on international issues. By doing so, it was found that students showed improvement in their ability to think critically as they engaged with the content through peer learning activities. Through the

peer feedback activities increased awareness of the necessity to critically analyze materials also increased. Coyle's (1999) Four Cs Framework was used in the planning stage for the project and as a reference to assess its effectiveness.

Results from one-to-one interviews and observations from the facilitator indicate that the participants believed their ability to deliver their opinions in terms of fluency and accuracy using the content improved. The participants also stated that peer interaction was beneficial in the process. This outcome echoes MacGregor's (2016) interview study with university CLIL teachers in Japan that found that CLIL promotes peer cooperation. Finally, participants reported more significant levels of understanding of international issues and recognition of their own impact on such issues. These outcomes illustrate a connection with the Four Cs Framework used to plan the project. By providing students with appropriate content at their level and designing tasks that aid in the comprehension of that content, an equitable balance of content and language learning can be achieved.

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